

Complex Compounds of Substituted Thioureas. Part IV. Copper Derivatives of Mono-*N*-phenylthiourea and Di-*N*-phenylthiourea

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Complex compounds of mono- and di-*N*-phenylthioureas with different copper salts have been described and their properties studied. A critical analysis of the results of the investigation on complex compounds of mono- and di-substituted thioureas with copper salts, using acetyl and phenyl group as substituted has also been made.

As reported earlier¹, nine different types of copper-thiourea and copper-substituted thiourea compounds have so far been recorded in the literature. In these cases, besides solid mononuclear cuprous salt, many stable polynuclear derivatives, containing even fractional molecules of thiourea per metal ion, are reported to exist.

Various attempts made to solve the problem of constitution of the metal-thiourea complexes have been reviewed in Part III of this series², where the concept presented by Siddhanta and Banerjee¹ that S atom present as thiocarbonyl group and not N atoms present as amide in the ligand, functions as donor, forming stable complexes sometimes involving thiocarbamide bridge through S atom by two co-ordinate bonds to two metal atoms, has been justified.

As an extension of our previous work³, an analogous study has been made in the present paper using mono- and di-*N*-phenylthioureas as co-ordinating ligands. Of the nine types of thiourea complexes, some of the types (2), (3), (6), and (9), using *N*-phenylthiourea, and a few of the types (6) and (9), using di-*N*-phenylthiourea as ligands, with hydroxide, chloride, sulphate, nitrate, and acetate salts of copper have been prepared in the present investigation. Of these, compounds (vide Experimental), No. (1), (3), (7), and (8) have been reported for the first time, whereas No. (2), (4), (5), and (6), though previously reported by early workers^{4,5}, have been prepared under new experimental conditions and reacting ratios. Only compound so far prepared between copper salt and di-*N*-phenylthiourea (PhThPh) seems to be CuCl₂.PhThPh⁴ and hence all compounds of this series presented in this paper are new compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-Phenylthiourea was prepared by the method of Williams³, m.p. 154°. (Found: N, 23.01. Calc. for C₆H₅NHCSNH₂: N, 18.43%). Di-*N*-phenylthiourea was of B.D.H. grade.

1. Siddhanta and Banerjee, *this Journal*, 1961, **38**, 747.
2. Banerjee and Sukthankar, *ibid.*, 1963, **39**, 107.
3. Bahasrabudhey and Krall, *ibid.*, 1942, **19**, 25.
4. Koschkin, *J. Gen. Chem., USSR.*, 1938, **8**, 1083.
5. "Cyanogen Compounds", p. 57.

These are slightly soluble in water but highly soluble in ether, acetone, or ethanol and are very stable.

Copper Derivatives of Mono-N-phenylthiourea

1. *Mono-(N-phenylthiourea)-aquo-copper(1) Hydroxide*.—An aqueous solution of copper nitrate (2 g.) was added to a 7 aqueous solution of *N*-phenylthiourea (3 g.) at room temperature, when a white turbid solution was obtained. This was made slightly alkaline with dilute ammonia solution, when a brown precipitate was formed. It was filtered, washed with water, dried, and analysed. [Found: Cu, 25.45, 25.59; N, 11.39, 11.42; S, 13.09, 13.03. Calc. for (1) $\text{CuOH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}_2\cdot\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Cu, 26.37; N, 11.61; S, 13.27% and for (2) $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}_2$: Cu, 25.47; N, 11.21; S, 12.81%]. Dehn⁶ had probably prepared the same compound under different experimental conditions in an alkaline medium, which was represented by formula (2), where copper is bivalent. Though analytical data suit the formulas (1) and (2), considering the reducing power of the thiourea ligand in an alkaline medium, formula (1) is more probable.

The compound is brown and decomposes above 100°. It does not react with cold dilute HCl or NaOH solutions, but hot solutions decompose it. It is sparingly soluble in water but soluble in acetone or ethanol.

2. *Bis-(N-phenylthiourea)-aquo-copper(1) Hydroxide*.—An aqueous solution of copper nitrate (2 g.) was made slightly alkaline to litmus with a dilute ammonia solution. This was then added dropwise to a saturated aqueous solution of *N*-phenylthiourea (3 g.) at room temperature, when an olive-green precipitate was formed. It was filtered, washed with water, dried, and analysed. The green compound changed to brown after few days. [Found: Cu, 15.86, 15.90; N, 14.13, 14.09; S, 15.59, 15.70. Calc. for (1) $\text{CuOH}\cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}_2\cdot\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Cu, 15.78; N, 13.91; S, 15.90% and for (2) $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2\cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}_2$: Cu, 15.83; N, 13.95; S, 15.94%].

A brown compound represented by formula $\text{CuOH}\cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}_2$ was obtained by Siddhanta and Banerjee⁷ under different experimental conditions from copper sulphate (1 g.) and *N*-phenylthiourea (6 g.) and it was diamagnetic. Since the green hydrate, in the present case, changes to brown on keeping (dehydration) and as thiourea is a reducing ligand, the compound may be represented by formula (1) above.

The substance is olive-green in colour and decomposes above 100°. It is decomposed by dilute HCl or NaOH solutions, especially when warmed. The compound is sparingly soluble in water but soluble in acetone, forming a stable brownish yellow solution.

3. *Bis-(N-phenylthiourea)-copper Chloride*.—An aqueous solution of cupric chloride (2.75 g.) was added dropwise with constant stirring to an ethanolic solution (15%) of *N*-phenylthiourea (2.5 g.) at about 0°, when the mixture turned milk-white and a yellow compound was formed. After keeping at ice-temperature for about 90 mins., it was filtered and washed successively with ice-cold water and acetone. It was then dried in air and analysed. (Found: Cu, 15.59, 15.65; N, 13.78, 13.99; Cl, 8.82, 8.78; S, 15.72, 15.94. $\text{CuCl}\cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}_2$ requires Cu, 15.78; N, 13.90; Cl, 8.80; S, 15.88%.)

The compound is stable, m.p. 180°. It does not react with cold dilute HCl or NaOH solution, but it turns black with hot alkali solution. The compound is insoluble in water, ethanol, or chloroform, but highly soluble in acetone.

4. *Pentakis-(N-phenylthiourea)-dicopper (I) Chloride*.—An aqueous solution of cupric chloride (2 g.) was added slowly to a boiling aqueous solution of *N*-phenylthiourea (7 g.), when a pale yellow precipitate was formed. The mixture was digested on a water bath for about 30 min., filtered, washed with water and then with ethanol, dried, and analysed. (Found: Cu, 13.41, 13.55; N, 14.69, 14.74; Cl, 7.18, 7.10; S, 16.40, 16.55. Calc. for $2\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 5\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}_2$: Cu, 13.25; N, 14.61; Cl, 7.40; S, 16.70%). The same compound was obtained by Siddhenta and Banerjee¹ at room temperature and was diamagnetic. Hence it is formulated as a cuprous derivative of *N*-phenylthiourea. The compound is very stable, m.p. 182°.

5. *Tris-(N-phenylthiourea)-copper Chloride*.—An ethanolic solution (50 ml) of cupric chloride (1.5 g.) was added slowly with stirring to a solution (500 ml) of *N*-phenylthiourea (5.5 g.) in the same medium, when a greenish yellow solution was formed and a yellow compound was precipitated. On keeping the solution for $\frac{1}{4}$ hour, it was filtered, washed successively with water, ethanol, and acetone, dried in air, and analysed. (Found: Cu, 11.36, 11.42; N, 15.01, 14.95; Cl, 6.30, 6.37; S, 17.21, 17.15. Calc. for $\text{CuCl} \cdot 3\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}_2$: Cu, 11.40; N, 15.14; Cl, 6.39; S, 17.30%). The same compound was prepared by Sahasrabudhey and Krall² in aqueous medium at about 100°.

The compound is stable, m.p. 190°. It does not react with dilute HCl or NaOH solutions, whereas hot solution decomposes it, forming a black residue. It is insoluble in water, ethanol, or chloroform and sparingly soluble in acetone.

6. *Hexakis-(N-phenylthiourea)-dicopper (I) sulphate* was obtained as a pale yellow, flocculent precipitate when a solution of copper sulphate (3 g.) was added slowly to that of *N*-phenylthiourea (6 g.) at room temperature. The product was filtered, washed with water and ethanol, dried in air, and analysed. (Found: Cu, 11.24, 11.29; N, 14.66, 14.75; S, 19.90, 19.84. Calc. for $\text{Cu}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 6\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}_2$: Cu, 11.19; N, 14.80; S, 19.73%). The same compound was obtained by earlier workers^{1,3} under different experimental conditions and it was found to be diamagnetic¹. Hence it is represented as a cuprous compound. It melts at 110°.

7. *Tris-(N-phenylthiourea)-copper nitrate* was obtained as a deep yellow, sticky precipitate when a hot solution of copper nitrate (3 g.) was added slowly with stirring to a boiling solution of *N*-phenylthiourea (7.5 g.). The mixture was kept at the boiling temperature for about 10 mins. It was filtered and washed successively with hot water and ethanol. The product was in a semisolid state while in hot solution, which on cooling turned into a hard, sticky mass. It was dried in vacuum and analysed. (Found: Cu, 10.75, 10.87; N, 16.65, 16.94; S, 16.39, 16.46. $\text{CuNO}_3 \cdot 3\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}_2$ requires Cu, 10.93; N, 16.85; S, 16.51%).

The compound is stable towards cold and hot dilute HCl and does not react with cold and hot dilute alkali, but hot solution decomposes it to a black residue. It is insoluble in water but soluble in ethanol and acetone. With chloroform, the substance turns into a sticky mass. It melts at 109–10°.

8. *Mono-(N-phenylthiourea)-copper Acetate*.—An aqueous solution of cupric acetate (2.5 g.) was added slowly with constant stirring to that of *N*-phenylthiourea (3 g.) at room temperature, when the colour of the solution changed from pale green to deep greenish blue with simultaneous formation of a buff-coloured precipitate. The mixture was allowed to stand for about an hour with occasional stirring. It was then filtered, washed with

water and finally with acetone. The product was dried in vacuum and analysed. (Found: Cu, 22.00, 23.10; N, 10.03, 9.98; S, 11.48, 11.73. $\text{CuOOCCH}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}_2$ requires Cu, 23.15; N, 10.20; S, 11.65%.)

The buff-coloured compound is not decomposed by cold dilute HCl or NaOH solution, but is decomposed in hot solutions, forming a black residue. The compound is insoluble in water, ethanol, and chloroform, but is sparingly soluble in acetone. It melts at 110° .

Copper Derivatives of Di-N-phenylthiourea

9. *Mono-(di-N-phenylthiourea)-copper Hydroxide*.—An acetone solution of copper nitrate (2 g.) was made just neutral with dilute ammonia solution, using litmus as indicator. It was then added slowly with stirring at room temperature to an acetone solution of di-N-phenylthiourea (4 g.), when the colour of the solution first changed to brown, then to green, and finally a shining orange product appeared. The mixture was kept for about 15 minutes, then filtered, washed with acetone, and analysed when dry. [Found: Cu, 20.75, 20.68; N, 9.09, 9.08; S, 10.48, 10.52. Calc. for (1) $\text{CuOH} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2$: Cu, 20.60; N, 9.07; S, 10.36% and for (2) $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2$: Cu, 19.46; N, 8.57; S, 9.80%]. Analytical data confirm formula (1) rather than (2). Dehn⁶ had probably prepared the same compound in an alkaline medium, which was represented as $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{PhThPh}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{PhThPh} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ on the basis of analysis of copper alone. From the same consideration as in compound No. 1 above, formula (1) representing copper as monovalent seems to be more justified.

The orange compound is stable towards cold dilute HCl and NaOH solutions, but hot solutions decompose it to a black residue. The substance is insoluble in water, ethanol, or acetone and soluble in chloroform.

10. *Bis-(di-N-phenylthiourea)-copper Chloride*.—A solution of cupric chloride (2 g.) in absolute ethanol was added slowly at room temperature to a solution of di-N-phenylthiourea (4 g.) in the same medium, when a pale yellow precipitate was formed. This was filtered, washed with ethanol, dried in air, and analysed. (Found: Cu, 11.32, 11.54; N, 9.94, 10.01; Cl, 6.31, 6.36; S, 12.06, 11.85. $\text{CuCl} \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2$ requires Cu, 11.45; N, 10.09; Cl, 6.39; S, 11.53%). The same compound was formed in an identical condition in absolute acetone. (Found: Cu, 11.28, 11.34; N, 10.06, 10.02; Cl, 6.33, 6.35; S, 11.45, 11.39%.)

The compound is stable in hot or cold dilute HCl and is decomposed by a hot dilute alkali solution. It is sparingly soluble in water or ethanol and highly soluble in acetone or chloroform.

11. *Bis-(di-N-phenylthiourea)-dicopper Sulphate*.—A hot aqueous solution of copper sulphate (2 g.) was added slowly with constant stirring to a boiling solution di-N-phenylthiourea (3.4 g.), when a grey precipitate was formed. It was filtered immediately, washed with hot water and finally with ethanol, dried in air, and analysed. (Found: Cu, 18.85; N, 8.20; S, 14.25. $\text{Cu}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2$ requires Cu, 18.70; N, 8.24; S, 14.14%.)

The compound does not react with cold dilute HCl or NaOH solutions, but hot solutions decompose it. It is insoluble in water, sparingly soluble in ethanol, and highly soluble in acetone or chloroform.

12. *Tetrakis-(di-N-phenylthiourea)-dicopper Sulphate*.—Anhydrous copper sulphate (2 g.) was dissolved in 50% ethanol (75 ml) and was added slowly with constant stirring to a boiling ethanolic solution (250 ml) of di-*N*-phenylthiourea (7 g.), when a grey compound was precipitated. The mixture was kept hot for about 15 mins. with occasional stirring. It was filtered, washed with ethanol, dried in vacuum, and analysed. (Found: Cu, 17.16, 17.38; N, 15.06, 15.20; S, 21.65; 21.83. $\text{Cu}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 4\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNHC}_6\text{H}_5$ requires Cu, 17.29; N, 15.24; S, 21.76%).

The compound does not react with cold and hot dilute HCl as also with cold dilute NaOH solution. With hot NaOH solution it turns black. It is insoluble in water, ethanol, and chloroform and sparingly soluble in acetone. It melts at 120° (decomp.).

13. *Mono-(di-N-phenylthiourea)-copper Acetate*.—Cupric acetate (1.15 g.), dissolved in 50% ethanol (50 ml), was added dropwise with stirring to an ice-cold ethanolic solution (650 ml) of di-*N*-phenylthiourea (4 g.), when a black-coloured solution was formed, which slowly changed to yellow, and finally a brick-red compound was precipitated. The mixture was kept at ice-temperature for about 25 mins., filtered, washed with cold ethanol, dried in air, and analysed. On drying, the colour changed from brick-red to deep yellow. (Found: Cu, 17.94, 18.05; N, 7.86, 7.95; S, 8.97, 9.01. $\text{CuOOCCH}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNHC}_6\text{H}_5$ requires Cu, 18.13; N, 7.99; S, 9.13%).

The compound melts at 114°. It is stable towards cold dilute HCl and NaOH solutions, but hot solutions decompose it. It is insoluble in water and ethanol and with the latter it changes from yellow to brick-red. It is sparingly soluble in acetone and soluble in chloroform, producing a stable reddish yellow solution.

DISCUSSION

It would be of interest to analyse the results of the investigation recorded in Parts I¹, III¹, and IV, wherein all possible attempts were made to prepare solid compounds of different classes by the reaction of chloride, acetate, sulphate, or nitrate of copper with mono- or disubstituted thioureas, using acetyl or phenyl groups as substituents. The results of the investigation are represented in Table I.

TABLE I

Ligand.	Ratio (M: ligand).						Total No.	
	(1 : 1).	(1 : 1.5).	(1 : 1.75).	(1 : 2).	(1 : 2.5).	(1 : 3).		(1 : 4).
AcTh	2	1	1	4	1	3	1	13
PhTh	3	1	..	2	1	3	1	11
AcThAc	..	..	..	1	..	..	1	2
PhThPh	3	..	..	2	..	..	..	5
Total No.	8	2	1	9	2	6	3	31

N.B. M=copper; Ac=acetyl; Ph=phenyl; Th=thiourea.

From a critical survey of the above table the following remarks may be noted:

(1) No solid compound of the types 4 (ratio, Met.: lig.=1:2.33) and 5 (1:2.2) could be prepared, whereas only one compound of type 7(1:1.75) has been obtained. Probably

compounds of these types are not true compounds but mixtures. Compounds of other classes, however, seem to be definite compounds as several of them have been prepared under different experimental conditions.

(2) No tetra-co-ordinated solid cuprous compound has been obtained with di-*N*-phenylthiourea as a co-ordinating ligand, though from a theoretical point of view, the formation of such a compound is expected since the cuprous ion is eight electrons short of the krypton structure which it can acquire by being co-ordinated with four molecular proportion of the thio-base. The large volume occupied by the two phenyl radicals probably produces a steric strain in the co-ordination zone round the cuprous ion, thus decreasing the stability of the solid complex. It is, however, strange that no solid compound containing four simple thiourea molecules per copper atom has yet been obtained, though the principal ion in solution for the various thiourea complexes⁷ is $[\text{CuTh}_4]^+$.

(3) Of the thirty one solid compounds prepared in the present series of investigations under all possible experimental conditions, the number of compounds formed with different substituted thioureas decreases in the order: $\text{AcTh} > \text{PhTh} > \text{PhThPh} > \text{AcThAc}$. Assuming that the formation of a stable solid complex as an index of its stability, it may be remarked that tendency for co-ordination of the thio-base with cuprous ion decreases in the same order and this co-ordinating capacity also falls with an increase of the number of substituents in the parent ligand.

The above observation confirms Riley's theory⁸ that any factor, which increases localisation of negative charge in the co-ordinating ligand, increases ability of the ligand to co-ordinate; this has also been confirmed by several other studies⁹. Considering -I and +E effects of the phenyl substituent on thiourea, it seems that the order of increasing basicity among the phenyl-substituted thioureas should be "phenyl < diphenyl" and this has been confirmed by Walter *et al.*¹⁰ in 50% dioxane solution [$pK(\text{PhTh})=2.80$; $pK(\text{Ph}_2\text{Th})=2.91$]. These two effects would additively affect (*i.e.*, decrease in the present case) the localisation of negative charge in the co-ordinating ligand and would therefore explain the co-ordinating capacity, *viz.*, " $\text{PhTh} > \text{PhThPh}$ ". The order " $\text{AcTh} > \text{AcThAc}$ " may also be explained, taking the inductive effect of the acetyl substituent into consideration. Comparing the chemical properties of organic compounds with phenyl and acetyl groups, it may be concluded that the phenyl group is less powerful than acetyl group in changing the basicity of thiourea and hence theoretically the order should be " $\text{PhTh} > \text{AcTh}$ ". The reverse order reported in the present work may, however, be due to comparative insolubility of the phenylthiourea and the larger volume of the phenyl radical, compared to acetyl radical functioning as substituents in the ligand.

(4) Amongst the compounds of classes (1), (2), (6), and (9), *i.e.*, metal: ligand as 1:4; 1:3; 1:2, and 1:1 respectively, it is of interest to note, that the number of complexes formed decreases in the order " $(1:2) > (1:1) > (1:3) > (1:4)$ ". The gradual decrease of the number of compounds with an increase in the number of ligands in the co-ordination sphere may be due to steric effect produced by the substituents in the ligand, even though four-

7. Lane *et al.*, *Anal. Chem.*, 1957, **29**, 481.

8. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2985.

9. Bruchlman *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1401; Bjerrum, *Chem. Rev.*, 1949 **46**, 381.

10. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 5560.

co-ordinated complex is expected theoretically (*vide infra*). The unusual stability of (1:2) complex in all the four series, however, requires further explanation.

(5) It may also be remarked from the review that the number of stable solid compounds formed between different thioureas and copper(II) ion is affected by the chemical nature of the anion and decreases in the order: " $\text{Cl}^- > \text{OH}^- > \text{CH}_3\text{COO}^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{NO}_3^-$ ". The nature of the anion and the ligand is therefore expected to influence the stability of such compounds.

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